

The following pictures visualize how data are distributed among 20 clients on different alpha values. The horizontal axis represents the client ID and the vertical axis represents the class labels. The sizes of circles indicate the number of samples per class allocated to each client. The smaller the alpha is, the more likely the clients hold samples from only one class (randomly chosen).



alpha = 0.1



alpha = 1



alpha = 10